

LEXICAL MEANS OF EXPRESSING POLITENESS IN TH ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Dilrabo Nazirqulova Zafariddin qizi
Abduvahobova Mahina Ozodxonovna

Scientific advisor:

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Annotation: the following thesis includes some valuable information about the expression of politeness category in the English and Uzbek languages. Lexical means of expressing politeness in both languages are somehow similar, the differences are also given with the help of some vivid examples.

Key words: politeness, level, greeting, apologizing, culture, expressions, language.

The expression of politeness in different levels are various, but learning them in each level make our research complex and perfect. So, analyzing of politeness in one language level, requires learning it from other levels, such as syntactic, grammatical and lexical levels. Because, every level has their own peculiarities, and place in the expression of politeness, and certainly, they complete each other in various ways. This part of our research is devoted to express the politeness from the lexical level. During our analyzing the language, we have found some examples of lexical means of expressing politeness in the English and Uzbek languages. One of the mostly used expressions of politeness in both languages can be observed in the situations, like greeting, apologizing, thanking, saying goodbye, refusing and congratulating. In such situations the representatives of both culture use stable expressions automatically, and these markers are taught to young children from their very early ages.

Let's consider some examples in English. English people, say "Good morning", "Hello", "How are you", "Hi", "Nice to meet you", "How do you do?", "How are you doing", "What's the news?" and other expressions when they are greeting with each other. The usage of such expressions as "Hi", "Hello", "How do you do?" are more frequent in socio-equal situations. Friends, relatives, neighbors and close people, greet with each other saying these words.

Saying "Good morning", "Good evening", "Good afternoon" according to the part of the day are typical for more formal situations, and when the conversation occurs between unfamiliar people, or with elderly people. Besides, these expressions, the usage of "welcome" can also be observed in the non-social situations. In Uzbek language, People, say "Assalomu aleykum", "Salom", "Salomatmisiz", "Bormisiz", "Qalesiz", "Yaxshimisiz?", "ishlaringiz yaxshimi?", and so on in greeting situations.

“Assalomu aleykum” is considered to be the neutral type of greeting, as it can be used between both youngsters and older generation. “Salom”, “Qalesiz”, “Qalesan” are the expressions that are mostly used among very close friends, and equal-aged people, and certainly, the degree of closeness is dominated when using these greeting markers. The word formation of the words “Qalesiz” and “Qalesan” are formed by adding to the root morpheme “Qale-”, the suffixes of the 2nd person in singular “san” and plural “siz”. The usage of the words “Qalesan”, “Qalesiz” was firstly observed when communicants ask each other’s health, condition and mood. Nowadays, they are used as the starters of the conversation and can be applied as the equivalents of greeting expressions like “Assalomu aleykum”, “Salom” and so on. One of the greeting words “Salom” in Uzbek was formed by the way of abbreviation. It is the short way of saying “Assalomu aleykum” and is mainly used in everyday communication of close friends and relatives.

In some greeting situations, the Uzbeks say “Keling”, “Xush kelibsiz”, “marhamat”, “uyga kiring” and other stable expressions in order to show that they are pleased about their coming, and ready for welcoming them in their home.

The distinction between “siz” and “sen” in Uzbek language can not be observed in English. The usage of “you” for both equal-aged and elder people is acceptable in this very language.

In the circumstances like apologizing, English people use some expressions such as “Excuse me”, “I’m sorry”, “Forgive me”, “I apologize for”, “I beg your pardon”, “Pardon me”.

The expression of “Excuse me” is mostly used when the speaker wants to interrupt the interlocutor, or ask for help. But, “I’m sorry”, “sorry” are typical for the situations that have already occurred.

“Excuse me, would you mind if I opened the window?”

“I’m sorry never meant to hurt you”

“Sorry that all this happened.”

Another apologizing markers “forgive me”, and “I apologize for” are accounted as more formal ways of expressing apologize and mostly used in letters, and expresses stronger type of apologize, as they have strong emotional coloring. In order to enhance the degree of apologize with the help of these markers, we can add some amplifiers, as *so, very, dreadfully, awfully, really, terribly*.

“I’m so sorry that I couldn’t attend your yesterday’s party.”

"I'm really sorry would you ever forgive me?"

"I beg your pardon" is much more polite form of apologizing, and is not frequent in everyday communication.

In Uzbek, we use *"Kechiring", "Kechirasiz", "Uzr", "Ming bor uzr", "Hijolatdaman", "ma'zur tuting", "bir qoshiq qonimdan keching", "Uzrimni qabul qiling"*

"Kechiring", "kechirasiz" are more frequent and neutral in Uzbek communication and don't matter age differences. As English expression *"Excuse me"*, they can be used when the speaker interrupts the interlocutor and wants to excuse.

"Kechirasiz, shu yerda ruchkam qolib ketmabdimi ?, ko'rib bera olasizmi"

"Uzr", "Hijolatdaman" are also often used between interlocutors, who don't know each other very well and have age distinction.

"Uzr" in Uzbek is borrowed from Arabic word, and as a result of changing some letters of Arabic, into Uzbek, the form of *"uzr"* is applicable in Uzbek language, the meaning of which is *"the basis for being forgiven, justified"* and is used to ask to be excused by someone in everyday communication. [Sh. Rakhmatullayev, "O'zbek tilining etimologik lug'ati", 2003]

The expressions *"Ming bor uzr", "ma'zur tuting", "bir qoshiq qonimdan keching"* are more formal and fictional ways of apologizing and have strong stylistic and emotional coloring. These kind of apology markers were mostly used in the fictional works of writers that describe ancient, historical times.

Thanking in English is expressed with the clichés such as *"thank you", "thanks", "thanks a lot", "Thank you very much", "I'm grateful for..", "I'm obliged for...", "I appreciate you...", "I would like to thank you..."*

The neutral expressions are *"thank you", "thanks", "thanks a lot", "thank you very much"*, that are used in all thanking situations. But, the others are used in special situations due to their high degree of formality.

The gratitude expressions in Uzbek are *"rahmat", "tashakkur", "minnatdorman", "ming rahmat"*. In speech we can frequently see the word *"rahmat"*, as it is considered to be neutral and mostly used one during the conversation. Moreover, we can add some words and expressions as *"Barakalla!", "Ofarin!", "Otangizga rahmat!", "Yashang!"* that may be used in such gratitude situations. The meaning of these expressions along with the meaning of gratitude is near for praising, boosting the interlocutor.

Taking all the things into consideration, we should note that the expression of politeness with the help of syntactic, semantic and lexical means, help us to construct friendship atmosphere with our interlocutor and give the chance of achieving our intentions during the conversation.. The normative vocabulary of the language plays an important role in forming lexical level of politeness. The universal lexical means of politeness are clichés, stereotypes and standard phrases that are absorbed in the communication of any language. Accordingly, it should be noted that, the category of politeness depends on the structure and culture of the language, and misusing means of its expression, speaker destroys the harmony of statements and cannot achieve his desired goal.

The list of used literature:

1. Sh. Rakhmatullayev, "O'zbek tilining etimologik lug'ati", 2003
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